

Paper 11

**FIRSTBELL PROGRAMME OF KERALA DURING COVID -19
PANDEMIC: AN ATTITUDINAL STUDY IN PRIMARY SCHOOL LEVEL**

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ABSTRACT

First Bell is an initiative of the General Education Department of Kerala, started on June 1, 2020 as an interim arrangement against the backdrop of State public schools remaining closed owing to the COVID-19 pandemic. It is aimed at ensuring that not a single student misses out on classes during pandemic and aims to safe stay of children at home. The investigators intend to study about the attitude of parents, teachers and students about this programme. The sample of the study includes 159 primary school students,149 parents of primary school students and 10 teachers who are employed in public schools Kerala. Used three tools including one questionnaire to parents and one questionnaire to children and an interview schedule for teachers. This study revealed that majority of the students, children and teachers favored this unique venture of Government of Kerala with its merits. But there are some obstacles also pinpointed especially on poor network coverage and less control of parents over children. This study delimited to one district of Kerala. The finding helps educationalists, curriculum developers, teachers, parents and students of other states in India.

Key words: First Bell Programme, Primary schools, Kerala, Covid -19 Pandemic

1. Introduction

Kerala's classrooms have been at the fore front for the last few years. There are many reasons behind it. Infrastructure development and quality education made the enrolment better than previous years compared to other states in India for the last two consecutive years. The New Indian Express states that 1.63 Lakh students secured admission in government and aided schools in 2019 June. In class 5 ,44.636 and in class 8th ,38492 students joined. On January 13, 2016 The Vice President of India, Hameed Ali- Ansari announced in Thiruvananthapuram, that Kerala has become the first state in India to achieve 100% primary education. As per same ham, the complete School Databank and school wiki ,Wiki of each Individual schools shows The general education department ,Kerala directly manages 14000+ schools, 160000+

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teachers ,20000+ non-teaching staff of the state.

Public schools in Kerala include government schools and government-aided schools. Although international standards and high-tech buildings provided an environment for blended teaching and learning. The distance that Corona pandemic has brought has made technology even better. Teachers, parents and children accelerated learning through using technology in the field of education The first bell online classes conducted during pandemic, by the Government of Kerala, Department of Public Instruction were telecast through Victor's Channel and the children watched it live. For those who can't see on time, it can be rebroadcast and viewed via a YouTube link. This is a study of the systematic procedures for implementing the program to the children and the attitude of the student community, teachers and parents towards it.

2. Need and significance of the study

Achievements in maintaining the quality of education Kerala's classrooms are, no doubt appreciable. First Bell is an initiative of the General Education Department of Kerala, started on June 1, 2020 as an interim arrangement against the backdrop of State public schools remaining closed owing to the COVID-19 pandemic. The curriculum, text books, classroom, school environment etc. play an important role in teaching learning process. Educators and learners should adopt online methods for teaching and learning. The First bell programme of General Education department is implemented in such a way that transmission through Television and YouTube channel then elaboration classes of in schools and follow up assignments. In these three phases technological knowledge and internet facilities are essential along with suitable devices. The attitude of public is the main cause of concern. Their social, emotional, intellectual and economic backgrounds may support or withdraw from participating in it. So the investigator intends to study the possibilities, attitudes merits and demerits, of such a programme actualized by government of Kerala during corona pandemic.

3. Objectives of the study

- 1.To analyse the merits and demerits of first bell programme
- 2.To know the attitude of parents, students and teachers towards first bell programme
- 3.To know the constrains that faced by parents, teachers and pupils due to social, emotional, intellectual and economic backgrounds.
- 4.To familiarize with the online tools and techniques of online teaching and learning.

4. Operational definitions of key terms

4.1. First Bell programme

First Bell was launched by the General Education Department on June 1 as an interim arrangement against

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the backdrop of State schools remaining closed owing to the COVID-19 pandemic. It is aimed at ensuring that not a single student misses out on classes during pandemic E- classes telecasts through Victors education channel .VICTERS (Versatile ICT Enabled Resource for Students) was inaugurated by A P J Abdul Kalam ,the President of India on 28th July, 2005 in Thiruvananthapuram has revolutionized classroom methodology in the State. KITE (Kerala Infrastructure and Technology for Education) is a Govt of Kerala establishment set up to foster, promote and implement Modernisation of educational institutions in the State of Kerala, owned by the State or run under the aid of Government. . The Hindu daily, July 26th 2020 reports that as part of the programme, 604 classes have been aired through the KITE Victors channel, along with 274 Kannada medium classes and 163 Tamil medium classes telecast through local cable networks within July in the State. And In addition to the Victors channel viewership, the web-streaming platform of KITE Victors, www.victors.kite.kerala.gov.in has also seen a tremendous response — as many as 442 terabytes data has been accessed from 141 countries for 2 months June and July.

Behind this there is a group work by the channelizing agencies of education such as SCERT, Samagra Shiksha Kerala and DIET. They edit prepared scripts of teachers who handle the classes. School teachers Conducts explanatory classes and provides follow-up activities. This is done through the class group of What Sapp on the parent's mobile phone. Sometimes these activities done through Google Meet, or by utilizing other similar virtual classroom technologies. Television and mobile phones were provided to the children who are not having that facilities at home, by people’s representatives, officers well-wishers, NGO’s and the school family members. Classes are broadcasted in educational centers in Pnchayath areas where it is not possible to see by children at home. Few students presented there keeping a social distance. Thus, all type of preparations was made to make it accessible to all children.

4.2. The COVID-19 pandemic

Coronavirus pandemic is an ongoing pandemic . It was first identified in December 2019 in Wuhan, China. Millions of deaths attributed to COVID-19 at the beginning and this virus spread through contact. Corona symptoms are highly variable, ranging from none to severe illness. The virus is spreading mainly through the air, when people are near each other. It leaves an infected person as they breathe, cough, sneeze, or speak and enters another person via their mouth, nose, or eyes. It might also spread through contaminated surfaces. People remain infectious for up to two weeks, and can spread the virus even if they do not have symptoms. The authorities of different countries recommended different preventive measures. That including mainly social distancing, wearing a mask covering mouth and nose in public, ventilation and air-filtering, regular usage of hand wash, covering one's mouth when sneezing or coughing, disinfecting surfaces, and monitoring. And recommended self-isolation for people exposed or symptomatic. Authorities worldwide responded by implementing travel restrictions, lockdowns and facility closures. .

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Educational institutions have been fully closed in India and partially or fully in all over the world. Kerala government also declared lockdown from March 2019 and schools and colleges remained closed. So Government of Kerala implemented online classes named First bell programme started on June 1st 2020 which was the reopening day of schools in Kerala.

4.3. Primary schools, Kerala

Primary schools include first standard to 7th standard. Lower primary section includes first to 4th standard and upper primary includes 5th to 7th standard. As per the details in Same them, the complete data bank, there are 9382 primary schools in Kerala .1514848 students are studying in primary schools of Kerala and 66485 teachers are teaching in these educational institutions. Noon meal, egg, milk, free uniform, textbooks scholarships etc. are provided to students in these schools.

TABLE 1 (Details regarding Primary Schools, Kerala)

School type	Number of L.P.Schools	Number of students in L.P.Schools	Number of teachers in L.P.Schools	Number of Up schools	Number of students in U.P.Schools	Number of teachers in U.P.Schools
Govt	2749	241887	11,858	865	232240	9595
Aided	3896	443257	20,581	1872	597464	24451
Total	6645	685144	32439	2737	829704	34046

5. Hypothesis

- 1.The teachers are able to implement the online teaching strategies suggested as part of First Bell programme
- 2.Parents and students are emotionally, economically intellectually and socially sound to co-op with first bell online classes.
- 3.First Bell online classes are accepted by Teachers, parents and students

Population of the study

Primary level teachers, students receiving instruction through First Bell online classes and the parents of primary level students of Kerala

Sample

Students, teachers and parents of primary schools in Kannur district

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Table .2 (Sample selected for the study)

Total number of students	159
Total number of parents	153
Total number of teachers	10

6. Tools used for the study

- 1.Questionnaire (to students)
- 2.Questionnaire (to parents)
- 3.Interview schedule (to teachers)

7. Statistical Techniques used

Percentage analysis

Data collected through googleforms from teachers, students and parents

8. Analysis and interpretation of data

Analysis of data collected from students of primary schools of Kannur district

150 Students of Kannur district responded to questions.

TABLE 3. Tool No.1(Questionnaire to students)

Qn no	questions	Options and percentage of responses			
1.	Do you regularly watch Firstbell online classes?	Watch live through Victers channel 126(82.4%)	Watch through the link sent by the teacher 27(17.6%)	Going to talent centres to watch the classes 0%	Not seen 0%
2.	FirstBell online classes for me	I like it a lot 44(28%)	I like it 99(64.7%)	Less interested in watching 6(3.9%)	Do not like 4(2.6%)
3	Folllow-up activities which are given to me in FirstBell online classes	I do and send it to my teacher 125(81.7%)	Sometimes done and send it to my teacher 15(9.8%)	Is often done but it is not send it to my teacher 13(8.5%)	I do not do follow-up activities. 0%
4	Clearing my doubts after online class	Through discussion in the class WhatsApp group 52(34.2%)	through Google Meet 8(5.3%)	Asking to parents 89(58.6%)	I usually doesn't have doubts 3(2%)

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5	in the elaboration class conducted by the teacher after the first bell class	I attend regularly 131(89.7%)	I attend occasionally 12(8.2%)	I will attend only if the teacher insists 2(1.4%)	I do not attend. 1(0.7%)
6	First Bell Class for me	I like it 133(88%)	Seen only when someone forcing to see it 3(2%)	I like only some classes 11(7.3%)	I dislike those classes 4(2.6%)
7	Does the teacher correct your note books?	Once in a month 4(3%)	Once in a week 91(68.9%)	Occasionally 25(18.9%)	Never 12(9.1%)
8	What are the interruptions that you have to face in online classes	No difficulties 131(89.7%)	Lack of connectivity 12(8.2%)	Economic problems (1.4%)	Parents employment 1(0.7%)
9	Events conducted online at my school	Club activities and day celebrations 27(18.1%) 93(62.4%)	Webinars & quiz competitions 6(4%) 110(73.8%)	PTA, CPT and parents' orientations 96(64.4%)	Worksheet distribution 76(51%)

8.1. Interpretation of data collected from students

A total of 159 children responded to the questions. 147 of them revealed their names, 12 pupil responded anonymously. 151 answered in which class they are studying now. Eight of them do not ready to reveal their classes. 57% of pupil, that is 86 pupil are in Lower Primary category and 43% ,65 pupil are in Upper Primary category.

From the above responses and interpretations of children we can make a few generalisation

1. 100% students having facilities at their homes.
2. Most of them are liking the First Bell classes
3. Majority of the students are doing their home works
4. Parents takes a major role in academic activities
5. Teachers taking elaboration classes to clear the difficult portions
6. They overcome their initial problems
7. All schools are active in the online mode. They are conducting a lot of curricular and co-curricular activities during pandemic

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TABLE.4. Tool 2 Analysis of data collected from parents

qn.no	questions	Responses and percentage of responses			
1	Does your child regularly attend firstbell online classes?	Yes 137(94.5%)	No 0(0%)	Sometimes 8(505%)	Never 0(0%0
2	The media used to watch the class	Through mobile phone 17(11.7%)	Through television, Kite Victers channel 127(87.6%)	Using computers 1(0.7%)	Going to educational centres arranged at my village 0(0%)
3	While watching the FirstBell online classes and engaging in child’s learning I..	I am about to improve my knowledge 37(25.9%)	I understood about today’s learning methodology 66(45.8%)	I understood the difference between todays and past learning methods 72(50%)	There is no significant changes in me 2(1.4%)
4	My child using the phone more for	To play games 9(6.2%)	For learning 127(87.6%)	To use social media 5(3.4%)	For other purposes 4(2.8%)
5	My child using my mobile phone	Under my observation 118(81.4%)	For very essential purposes 25(17.2)	I can’t control his/her usage 2(1.4)	I dont know for what it is 0(0%)
5	First Bell online classes broadcast through the kite Victers channel for my child is	Understands quickly 51(35.2%)	teacher’s explanatory class is essential to understand 54(37.2%)	It is understood when repeating 40(27.6%)	Not understood 0(0%)
6	By watching First Bell classes repeatedly my child can	content become more clear 93(64.6%)	Nothing beneficial 0(0%)	Watching only once 26(18.1%)	Watching only through television 25(17.4%)
7	In the case of doing homework, my child...	Is far ahead 47(32.4%)	Average 94(64.8%)	Only do so occasionally 4(2.8%)	Does not 0(0%)
8	As a parent in the case of First Bell online classes	I’m so happy 32(22.4%)	School classes are better than this 103(72%)	No comments 7(4.9%)	Not satisfied 1(0.7%)

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9	Reasons why I like First Bell Class (you can tick any number of options for this question)	1. During the COVID-19 period, children sit and study safely at home 132(91.7%) 2. can attend the class of many teachers 75(52.1%)	3. Doing homework regularly. 50(34.7%) 4. It can be heard and understood repeatedly through the phone and computer 41(28.5%)	5. I do not like 5(3.5%)	
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8.2. Interpretation of data collected from parents

A total of 153 parents responded to the questions. 143 of them revealed their names, 10 parents responded anonymously. 142 parents answered in which class their children are studying now. 12 of them do not ready to reveal their kid's classes. 85.2% of parent's, that is 121 pupils are in Lower Primary category and 14.8% parents, 21 pupil are in Upper Primary category.

1. 95% of children regularly attend the First Bell classes
2. Not any children is lacking devices at their home to watch the online classes.
3. By watching First Bell classes parents get educated and they realized the difference between today's and past's methodology of teaching
4. 88% of children using their phone for study purposes
5. First Bell classes are more effective when teacher explains the difficult parts. Besides they can watch again it through YouTube.
6. In the case of doing homework some of them are lazy and not timely completing; but all of them are doing their assignments.
7. Majority of the parents like school days more than these locked down online classes.
8. First Bell classes helps children to sit at home and study safely.
9. Parents and children can attend the classes of many teachers.
10. First Bell classes can be heard and understood repeatedly through television, the mobile phone and computer.
11. The number of parents who dislike the First Bell classes are less than 5%

8.3. Analysis of data collected from teachers

Interview schedule given to 10 teachers

1. What are the merits and demerits of First Bell online classes?

Merits

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- *First Bell provides a learning platform that is an ongoing without any obstacles.
- * Class can be viewed and operated anywhere and at any time
- * There is no need to give Study leave for children because they have plenty of leisure time.
- * Technological knowledge of teachers, parents and students developed by the utilization of First bell classes and other related activities.
- *Through virtual class rooms, teacher can meet pupil by the use of Google meet, video call, etc.
- * Parents educated for children’s sake on being a part of First Bell.
- *Teachers Improved methods of teaching by watching a lot of other teachers’ class on First Bell programme.
- *Teachers can spend a lot of time with own family
- * The rest parts of content are easy to handle because the major portion is handling through First Bell
- *it is an opportunity not to start school activities.
- *Further activities and related activities can be given in detail (rather than in classrooms)

De merits

- * Lack of facilities like internet coverage area issues,lacking high quality mobile phones to parents
- * Not everyone can afford the recharge amount.
- *A few of pupil are less interested
- *Parents mobile phone are not available at day time

2. What are the other activities given to reach the transmission class to our children?

- 1.Followup activities, i.e Assignment, project ,other home works
- 2.Clearing all class-related doubts and queries in Google Meets and What Sapp group discussion
- 3.Provides guidance and assistance to parents.
- 4.Discussions with children,
- 5.Providing work sheets
- 6.After the broadcast class, elaboration classes conducted at the night for the convenience of the parents as well.
- 7.Provides follow-up activities, which done and sent by the children. Teachers read , edit and give necessary instructions on time.
- 8.Parents share videos of the children's experiments, experience and other activities to the class group.
- 9.children and parents can communicate to teacher personally
10. after class each day five minutes left to parents for commenting and clearing doubts
- 11.Regular contact with children and parents.

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3. What is the attitude of the children towards this class?

1. There is no such interest now as there was in the first phase of this. Because it is now limited to just the lecture method.
2. Fearless classroom,
3. At first, I was very interested. I can ensure the whole class's interest through keeping link from previous class to upcoming class
4. Pupil are satisfied
5. More than half of the children take the class seriously and participate in the discussion and send the follow-up activities given to them. The rest have less interest.
6. Some students are not satisfied
7. Most of the students are interested.

4. What is the attitude of the parents towards First Bell online classes?

1. Some of them are less interested
2. They give more priority to classroom teaching
3. Working parents and the uneducated have a hard time.
4. Not completely satisfied.
5. Online learning does not feel serious. Children are lazy. Loss of interest in reading.
6. The constant involvement of teachers enables parents to take the class seriously.
7. Initial interest seems to be waning
8. Excellent classes

5. Are there any children in your school who cannot see the class at all?

1. No.
2. No
3. No.
4. No
5. No.
6. Children of an alcoholic parent do not attend online classes. Not paying attention to finishing works.
7. Some of them may occur due to technical errors

6. Have First Bell Classes helped you as an innovative teacher? How?

1. Sure, First Bell class is very helpful
2. More and more teachers are focusing on observing, embracing, copying and self-evaluating the teaching methods. It is possible.

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3. By watching the classes of teachers from other districts we can understand different ways of approaching an activity.
4. Yes. I was able to see and apply different learning methods.
5. Yes. Is a good model class
6. Yes. I learned a few effective methods that I had not applied.

7. How much time do you have to spend on teaching activities each day?

1. 3 hours
2. 2 hours
3. More time probably than spending time at school having classes.
4. More than 3 hours
5. Maximum 5 hours
6. About four hours
7. 4-5 hours
8. 3 to 4 hours
9. 4 hours,
10. sometimes more

8. What do you think about the need to continue First Bell online classes?

1. It is better for teachers to take classes their own. It is very difficult for children to move the class at a low speed on a subject like First Bell Social science
2. In this situation it is very essential for learners
3. If there is no First Bell classes, there will be no integration system for children across the state.
4. The absence of First Bell online classes can lead to a situation where many pupils have no studies at all.
5. The First bell online classes are essential to ensure student's safety in pandemic.
6. To be continued
7. There must be online classes until school opens.
Children gets learning objectives through online classes
8. Continue until a classroom-friendly environment is possible.

9. How does technological knowledge affect descriptive classes and follow-up activities?

1. Able to handle classes with great confidence.
2. Explanatory classes can be given through media like Google Meet.
3. Technical knowledge is essential

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4. In the best way of teaching and learning in pandemic days

5. Good help of using technology

6. Technical knowledge is essential.

10. What are the problems faced by children and parents?

1. They all are not well equipped with devices

2. Parents cannot help the children in some times.

3. Working parents are unable to bring children up with activities.

They feel more stressed when compared to other children.

4. There are some children in our classes who are alone without being able to play with their friends.

Not everyone can provide the necessary learning aids for children.

5. Anxiety about stress, inability to control children and learning gap

6. Some children may experience it as a mechanical learning. Besides, they don't have a chance to come back here and ask questions. That's what evening classes are arranged for. But talking directly through online does not get as much result. Parents also find it difficult to get all things right to their children.

7. Parents find it difficult for children to be lazy in follow-up activities. This is overcome by the daily teacher's explanation classes.

8. Reading habit decreases.

9. Few parents find it difficult to control their children.

9. Findings

1. Those children were provided with Tele Vision or mobile phone who are not having them at their homes; so 100% of children having facilities to watch First Bell classes at their homes.

2. Above 90% of children are liking this safe mode classes during pandemic. But a few below 8 percentage are less interested.

3. Above 80% of students are regularly doing their home assignments. The rest are interested in games and a few are not under their parents control.

4. Parents takes a major role in academic activities

5. Teachers taking elaboration classes to clear the difficult portions

6. All schools are active in the online mode. They are conducting a lot of curricular and co-curricular activities during pandemic

7. 95% of children regularly attend the First Bell classes.

8. By watching First Bell classes parents get educated and they realized the difference between today's and past's methodology of teaching

9. 88% of children using their phone for study purposes

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10. First Bell classes are more effective when teacher explains the difficult parts. Besides they can watch again it through YouTube .

11. Majority of the parents like school days more than these locked down online classes.

12. First Bell classes helps children to sit at home and study safely.

13. The number of parents who dislike the First Bell classes are less than 5%

14. Teachers are very happy. They find out the following merits.

* First Bell provides a learning platform that is an ongoing without any obstacles.

* Class can be viewed and operated anywhere and at any time

* There is no need to give Study leave for children because they have plenty of leisure time.

* Technological knowledge of teachers, parents and students developed by the utilization of First bell classes and other related activities.

* Through virtual class rooms, teacher can meet pupil by the use of Google meet, video call, etc.

* Parents educated for children’s sake on being a part of First Bell.

* Teachers Improved methods of teaching by watching a lot of other teachers’ class on First Bell programme.

* Teachers can spend a lot of time with own family

* The rest parts of content are easy to handle because the major portion is handling through First Bell

* it is an opportunity not to start school activities.

* Further activities and related activities can be given in detail (rather than in classrooms)

From the data collected from teachers we can come in to some findings

(1) * Economical issues

Lack of facilities like internet coverage area issues, lacking high quality mobile phones to parents

* Not everyone can afford the recharge amount.

Emotional problems

* A few of pupil are less interested

(2) Social backgrounds

* Parents mobile phone are not available at day time, because majority of them are outside of home for earnings.

(3) intellectual backgrounds

All parents are not efficient to support children in academic areas. But a lot of parents can help the children. It makes an equilibrium in what Sapp groups cause disparities among the group.

Parent’s over control over children make them unaware of assignments because some parents themselves doing the home works of children. They think their children get more appreciation for doing correctly.

10. Delimitations of the study

First Bell programme is practiced in public schools of Kerala. from standard one to twelfth. The present study is practiced only up to standard seven. The data collected only from a few teachers, parents and children. Not included high school and higher secondary teachers, parents and students. The study is restricted to Kannur district of Kerala. So the researcher is delimiting the study to an attitudinal study of First Bell programme during corona pandemic in Primary school level.

11. ConclusionThe present study has been immensely rewarding process and it has helped the researcher to find answers to the doubts that occurred to a great extent. In addition to explore new methods benefitted for online teaching and learning.

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